
Reclaiming Indigenous Beliefs and Practices for Environmental Stewardship and Sustainability in the Cordillera

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the importance of Indigenous beliefs and practices in the Cordillera, Philippines, highlighting the necessity of maintaining cultural and spiritual ties to the land for environmental stewardship and sustainability. The research underscores the deep connection that Cordilleran communities have with their ancestral lands, regarded as sacred and vital for cultural identity and environmental management. By examining practices such as the muyong forest management system and other Indigenous rituals, the study illustrates the intertwining of spirituality and sustainability through traditional ecological knowledge. However, these practices are increasingly threatened by modernization, industrial activities, and the decline of traditional values. The study also investigates syncretism, where Indigenous beliefs merge with Christianity, resulting in unique perspectives on environmental ethics. The objectives include emphasizing the integration of traditional knowledge with modern conservation methods to foster sustainable development while honoring cultural heritage. The methodology involves a critical review of available written traditions sourced from the internet and libraries around Baguio City. Results indicate that syncretism offers a valuable framework for combining traditional and modern conservation approaches. The study concludes with recommendations for cooperation among Indigenous communities, policymakers, and scholars to protect land rights and create inclusive con-

servation strategies. This research underscores the significance of preserving Indigenous practices and adapting them to contemporary challenges, highlighting their role in addressing global environmental issues.

Keywords: Indigenous beliefs, environmental stewardship, traditional ecological knowledge, sustainable development, syncretism in beliefs.

INTRODUCTION

The decline of traditional ecological knowledge (TEK) and practices among Indigenous communities in the Cordillera, Philippines, poses a significant challenge to environmental stewardship and sustainability (Camacho et al., 2016; FAO, 2013). This study was conducted to address the critical need to reclaim and integrate these Indigenous beliefs and practices, which are deeply connected to the land and play a vital role in cultural identity and environmental management. Existing literature has highlighted the sacredness of ancestral lands and traditional practices like the *muyong* forest management system, which intertwines spirituality with sustainable environmental practices (Acabado, 2017; Camacho et al., 2016;). However, these practices are increasingly threatened by modernization, industrial activities (e.g., mining and logging), and the erosion of traditional values (Tauli-Corpuz, 2015; World Bank, 2021).

While some studies have explored the concept of syncretism—where Indigenous beliefs merge with Christianity—there remains a gap in understanding how these hybrid perspectives can inform modern conservation efforts (Acabado & Martin, 2020; Scott, 1988). Additionally, inconsistencies in the application and recognition of Indigenous knowledge in environmental policies, such as the Philippines' *Indigenous Peoples' Rights Act (IPRA)* of 1997, further complicate effective stewardship (Lynch, 2011; UNDRIP, 2007).

This research aims to address these gaps by critically analyzing the intersection of TEK and modern conservation methods. By focusing on the Cordillera region, this study emphasizes

the importance of collaboration among Indigenous communities, policymakers, and scholars to protect land rights and develop inclusive conservation strategies (UNESCO, 2020; United Nations, 2009).

Ultimately, the objective is to provide a framework that integrates traditional practices with contemporary approaches, fostering sustainable development while honoring and preserving cultural heritage.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a critical literature review methodology to analyze traditional ecological knowledge (TEK) and conservation practices in the Cordillera region, Philippines, synthesizing peer-reviewed articles, policy documents, and gray literature (e.g., NGO reports ancestral domain records). It employed systematic searches across academic databases using specific keywords. It applied critical discourse analysis and thematic coding to uncover patterns and power dynamics in how Indigenous knowledge is represented in conservation literature.

Ethical considerations focused on decolonizing methodologies and addressing conflicting narratives, particularly between state-led conservation efforts and Indigenous stewardship, through a political ecology lens.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Overview of the Cordillera Region

The Cordillera Region, located in Northern Luzon, Philippines, spans approximately 1.75 million hectares and includes the provinces of Abra, Mountain Province, Kalinga, Apayao, Ifugao, Benguet, and the city of Baguio, with a population of about 1.3 million (Rimando 2015). This region, renowned for its rich mineral deposits like gold and copper, is also a crucial source of several major rivers such as the Chico, Agno, and Abra. Historically covered by dense forests, which have since diminished, the Cordillera's rugged terrain limits extensive agricultural use.

The region is the ancestral land of the Indigenous peoples collectively known as the Igorots, encompassing seven major ethnolinguistic groups, including the Kankanaeys, Bontocs, Kalingas, Ifugaos, Tingguians, Apayao (Isneg) and Ibaloy each have distinct socio-cultural systems and territories (Igorotage 2024; PSA-CAR 2024).

The Igorots of the Cordillera are Indigenous People with a unique culture passed down through generations (Molintas 2019). During a discussion at the University of the Philippines in Baguio, a woman challenged the speaker's use of the term 'Cordillera,' expressing a preference for 'Igorot' instead (Abad 2004). This incident highlighted a misunderstanding about 'Igorot.'

Sometimes linked to stereotypes and ethnocentrism. Additionally, Scott (1977) noted that for some, 'Igorot' can carry a derogatory implication of being pagan and uncivilized (p. 52). However, this does not accurately reflect their identity (Del Castillo et al., 2023).

A deep connection to their land marks their culture. It is characterized by communal land management, subsistence agriculture, and communal solid values. Traditional socio-political systems emphasize consensus and respect for elders, with rituals underscoring the sanctity of life and death (Molintas 2019). Despite the erosion of traditional systems due to external and internal pressures, the indigenous people's bond with their land remains robust. The Cordillera also hosts a notable non-indigenous population, mainly in Baguio and provincial town centers, alongside indigenous communities living near regional boundaries (Del Castillo et al., 2023). The cultural significance of the Cordillera is equally profound. This region is home to a variety of indigenous groups, each with distinct languages, traditions, and social structures. Among the prominent indigenous groups are the Ifugao, Kankanaey, and Ibaloi. These groups have developed a unique cultural identity closely tied to their environment, reflected in their traditional practices and belief systems (Carling 2001).

The Ifugao are perhaps best known for their elaborate rice terraces, which are considered engineering marvels and are rec-

ognized as UNESCO World Heritage Sites. The Ifugao rice terraces, built over 2,000 years ago, exemplify a sophisticated system of irrigation and terracing that demonstrates their deep understanding of sustainable agricultural practices and environmental stewardship (Scott 1977, 52). This ancient agricultural system is a testament to their engineering skills. It reflects their spiritual connection to the land, where agriculture is interwoven with ritual and community life (Camacho et al. 2016, 7).

The Kankanaey, residing primarily in the western part of the Cordillera, are known for their intricate weaving and vibrant cultural rituals. Their social organization is based on a communal system where kinship ties and ancestral traditions play a central role in maintaining harmony within their communities (Sitabayasi 2022). Kankanaey culture is marked by its rich oral traditions, ceremonial practices, and a deep reverence for ancestral spirits, which are integral to their worldview and daily life (Domogen nd; Sitabayasi 2022).

The Ibaloi people, part of the Indigenous groups in the Cordillera, have distinct cultural practices, including unique clothing, rituals, and gold mining traditions, which reflect their environment and beliefs (Sumeg-and 2005; "Ibaloi People" 2024). Their social and religious practices are intertwined with their spiritual beliefs, especially in the context of feasts and ceremonies like the *cañao*. Their traditional music forms, such as the Jew's harp and nose flute, are considered sacred in these rituals (Ibaloi People - Wikipedia 2024). They are recognized for their elaborate burial practices and ceremonies that reflect their beliefs about life, death, and the afterlife (Abordo and Coronation 2019). The Ibaloi communities practice a form of animism where natural elements and ancestors are believed to have spiritual significance, guiding their agricultural and social activities (Laugrand et al. 2020).

The Cordillera's indigenous peoples have historically maintained their cultural practices despite external pressures from colonization and modernization (Peterson 2010). Their traditional ecological knowledge has played a crucial role in preserving the region's biodiversity and promoting sustainable environmental practices. This knowledge is passed down through

generations and is deeply embedded in their cultural rituals and daily lives (Ting et al., 2008).

The Cordillera region stands out for its geographical grandeur and cultural richness. Indigenous groups such as the Ifugao, Kankanaey, and Ibaloi embody a deep connection to their environment through traditional practices and belief systems (Anacin 2009; Peterson 2010). Understanding their way of life provides valuable insights into the region's cultural and ecological significance, highlighting the importance of preserving their heritage and integrating their knowledge of contemporary environmental stewardship.

Cultural and Religious Contexts

Before the arrival of Christianity in the Cordilleras, the indigenous peoples, including the Ifugao and other Igorot groups, practiced animism. Their belief system revolved around the idea that spirits inhabited nature and that the forces of the natural world were sacred and interconnected with human life (Britannica 2024; NativeTribe.info n.d.). This animistic worldview imbued daily life with reverence for natural elements such as mountains, rivers, and forests, which were seen as home to ancestral spirits and deities. These beliefs informed their agricultural practices, rituals, and community organization, fostering a deep spiritual connection to the land (Britannica 2024; NativeTribe.info n.d.).

The transition from animism to the adoption of Christianity was marked by resistance in some parts of the Cordillera, with many communities integrating Christian beliefs with their indigenous practices, creating a unique blend of spirituality. However, the core animistic values emphasizing nature's sanctity and the guardianship of ancestors over the land remained influential in the region's cultural identity (Yzagada 2021; "Igorot People" 2024).

Studying Indigenous environmental practices within cultural and religious contexts is crucial for understanding their full significance and potential applications (Kimmerer 2013; Sinthumule 2023). Indigenous environmental stewardship is often intertwined with religious beliefs and rituals that promote ecologi-

cal harmony. In the Cordillera, ancestor reverence plays a significant role in environmental management (Sacredness of Nature 2024; Adivasi.org 2024). These practices are rooted in a belief system that views ancestors as guardians of the land, thus ensuring that environmental stewardship is a communal and sacred responsibility (Taray 2008). This perspective contrasts sharply with Western approaches, often separating spiritual beliefs from environmental management (Global Diversity Foundation 2021).

Understanding these practices within their cultural and religious contexts provides valuable insights into their effectiveness and sustainability. For example, Ifugao's forest management practices are guided by spiritual beliefs that emphasize the interconnectedness of all life forms (Yodisphere 2022). These beliefs foster a sense of stewardship that extends beyond immediate human needs to encompass long-term ecological health (Camacho et al. 2016). This holistic approach underscores integrating cultural values with environmental policies to achieve sustainable outcomes.

The spiritual dimensions of these practices contribute to their effectiveness by fostering a deep sense of responsibility and connection to the environment. Auger (2016) argues that cultural continuity, including traditional environmental practices, determines Indigenous health and well-being. This continuity ensures that environmental stewardship is embedded in the daily lives of Indigenous communities, reinforcing sustainable practices.

The history of religious groups and missionaries in the Cordillera region of the Philippines reflects a complex interplay of indigenous traditions and external influences. Early Spanish missionaries in the 16th century sought to Christianize the Igorot people, yet their efforts were resisted mainly due to the mountainous terrain and strong indigenous beliefs (Scott 1974).

By the American colonial period in the early 20th century, Protestant missionaries introduced educational and health programs, mainly through the Episcopal Church, which established a significant presence in the region (Wiber 1991, 49). Catholic missions, however, persisted and expanded under orders like the CICM (Congregation of the Immaculate Heart of Mary), which

built institutions like Saint Louis University to serve as centers for education and evangelization ("Saint Louis University Baguio City History & Institutional Statements" 2024). These missionary activities were often met with tension as they sought to supplant indigenous spiritual practices. However, they also contributed to socio-economic development in the Cordillera. Today, Christian and indigenous spiritualities coexist, reflecting the region's pluralistic religious landscape.

In the study by Del Castillo et al. (2023), these Indigenous Peoples possess distinct cultural traditions and religious beliefs. The Cordilleran inherit these practices from their elders and integrate them into their everyday lives (Camacho et al. 2016; Del Castillo et al. 2023). Their religious practices involve animal sacrifices, offerings to ancestral spirits, and herbal remedies (Celino 1990). These beliefs also influence their approach to environmental conservation, as they consider nature sacred and emphasize protecting and preserving it (Molino, 2022).

Cordilleran Indigenous people navigate a blend of traditional religious beliefs and modern practices, particularly Christianity. While many have adopted Christianity, they often integrate their Indigenous traditions into their Christian practices, resulting in hybrid religious expressions (Aguilar 2018; Del Castillo et al. 2023). This fusion illustrates the complexity of religiosity among Cordilleran. It highlights the interplay between their cultural heritage and contemporary spiritual practices. Understanding this blend offers insights into their cultural identity, values, and environmental attitudes (Del Castillo et al. 2023).

Socio-cultural, Religious, and Political Challenges

In continuing research on Indigenous beliefs and environmental stewardship of people worldwide, cultural and religious challenges are inevitable as part of local experiences. Experts (Buchler & Rossi 1980; Friedl & Pfeiffer 1977, 283-284; Champagne 2007, 79) argue that Indigenous peoples have rich and diverse cultures based on a profound spiritual relationship with their land and natural resources. They claim that indigenous societies do not have dichotomies such as nature vs. culture. Indigenous peoples do not see themselves as outside the realm of nature. However, in the contemporary era, I observe that in Cordil-

lera, in the northern part of the Philippines, social, religious, and political institutions have greatly affected the traditional ways of the Indigenous people. Traditionally, one salient characteristic of Indigenous cultures is that they are based on a collective perspective; today, this might no longer be the case.

Since the advent of modernity and economic capitalism, the Indigenous traditional religious and cultural practices have been threatened by individualism and the claim for private property. Capitalism is an economic system marked by private ownership of property and driven by profit motives (Dimonye 2024). This individualistic and capitalist mentality resulted in environmental problems of biodiversity loss, ecosystem collapse, and climate change (Pollock 202). These environmental problems were being intensified by so-called development programs that are designed for resource extraction, especially in the homelands of indigenous peoples. Bilateral and multilateral aid agencies, along with multinational corporations, often implement projects that disregard indigenous rights and their deep connection to nature, leading to resistance that is frequently suppressed through force, deception, or state military intervention.

The encroachment of free market capitalism primarily drives the erosion of traditional ecological and spiritual values in Indigenous communities (United Nations 2009). These communities, which once united against external threats like corporations and corrupt government officials seeking to exploit their ancestral lands, are now adopting the values they previously opposed. Younger generations, swayed by capitalist ideals, increasingly see their land as a resource to be exploited for profit, undermining the community's deep spiritual connection to the land. This change weakens the communities' ability to resist outside pressures and creates internal rifts, as some members support resource extraction. In contrast, others strive to protect the land.

Gregory E. Sterling (2024) emphasizes that addressing issues requires more than scientific or political efforts; it demands a profound ethical and spiritual transformation. He argues that humanity's responsibility as stewards of creation, the imperative for intergenerational equity, and the need for social justice—

especially for people experiencing poverty disproportionately affected by climate change— necessitate action led by moral conviction and community engagement, akin to the religious leadership in the civil rights movement.

Significance of Studying Indigenous Practices

Indigenous knowledge can be broadly defined as the knowledge that an indigenous (local) community accumulates over generations of living in a particular environment (Ryser 2011). In the Philippines, indigenous groups like the Ifugaos of the Cordillera Mountains continue to thrive in their self-sufficient communities. Despite changes in Indigenous knowledge systems, practices promoting forest sustainability remain strong (Camacho et al., 2013). Studying Indigenous environmental practices is not only an academic exercise but a practical necessity in the face of global environmental challenges. As climate change and ecological degradation intensify, there is growing recognition of the value of Indigenous knowledge systems in addressing these issues. Preserving and applying traditional ecological knowledge can enhance contemporary environmental strategies and contribute to more effective conservation practices (Bennett et al., 2018).

Indigenous knowledge provides critical insights into sustainable resource management practices, offering valuable contributions to holistic and practical solutions (Patterson et al., 2023). Collaborative conservation initiatives involving Indigenous communities have achieved superior environmental conservation and community well-being outcomes. Integrating diverse knowledge systems, such as religious beliefs, alongside Indigenous wisdom can foster innovative approaches and mitigation strategies for addressing longstanding environmental challenges (Patterson et al., 2023). In forest management contexts, indigenous knowledge offers profound insights into local ecosystems, essential for safeguarding natural resources (Yahaya 2013). Incorporating traditional practices in geopark management also enhance community engagement and foster the preservation of cultural heritage (Halim et al. 2017).

Indigenous Beliefs and Worldviews in the Cordillera

In Cordilleran beliefs, the land is considered sacred, with a profound cultural and spiritual significance. The concept of ancestral domains is central to their worldview. These domains are not seen as private property but as sacred heritage passed down through generations. They represent a continuum of life, culture, and identity (Santiago 2013).

Rituals and ceremonies are crucial for maintaining the sanctity of the land. For example, the *pagtatawid* ceremony, which involves the transfer of land stewardship, is performed to seek the approval of ancestral spirits. This ceremony ensures that new stewards respect and uphold the land's sanctity, highlighting the sacred relationship between the Cordillerans and their ancestral domains (ICBE n.d.). Such practices are spiritual and practical, ensuring the land is managed sustainably. By integrating rituals with land management, the Cordillerans balanced spiritual and ecological needs, demonstrating a holistic approach to environmental stewardship (Agbayani 1993).

Allad-iw (2014) explains that for the Cordillerans, land is not merely a resource but a fundamental aspect of their identity, culture, and existence. Their ancestral lands encompassing territories, waters, and resources are considered sacred and integral to survival. This deep connection is rooted in their traditional practices of sustainable resource management and collective ownership, where land is seen as a shared inheritance passed down through generations. The Cordillerans' relationship with their ancestral lands is not defined by individual ownership but by collective responsibility and stewardship (Carling 2001; Cordillera Peoples Alliance, n.d.). Their struggle for land rights stems from a historical context of colonial dispossession and a continued fight against development projects that threaten their way of life. The concept of land for the Cordillerans is not simply about ownership but about preserving their cultural heritage, ensuring their future, and maintaining a harmonious balance with the environment (Alad-iw 2014; Pacos 2018). The discourse on land and resources among the Cordillera peoples can only be understood within the context of their beliefs and day-to-day practices.

"To claim a place is the birthright of every man. The

lowly animals claim their place; how much more man? Man is born to live. *Apu Kabunian*, lord of us all, gave us life and placed us in this world to live human lives. Moreover, where shall we obtain life? From the land. To work the land is an obligation, not merely a right. In tilling the land, you possess it. Thus, land is a grace that must be nurtured. The land is sacred. The land is beloved. From its womb springs our Kalinga life" ("The Cordillera People Right to Land" 2024).

These were the words of a Kalinga warrior chief, Macliing Dulag, explicitly describing the Cordillera peoples' concept of land. Like most Indigenous peoples worldwide, the Cordillera peoples equate land with life, both given by the Creator. Land, in this sense, includes all the resources below and above the earth's surface ("The Cordillera People's Right to Land," 2024).

Indigenous environmental stewardship is characterized by a deep connection to the land and a holistic view of ecological systems. Traditional practices, such as cultural burning and rotational farming, are grounded in extensive knowledge accumulated over generations. For example, Adlam et al. (2022) emphasize the role of Indigenous cultural burning in managing fire regimes to enhance biodiversity and reduce wildfire risks. These traditional methods often outperform modern approaches in terms of ecological sustainability and resilience (Adlam et al., 2022).

In the Cordillera region, the Ifugao people's forest management practices are informed by spiritual beliefs that underscore the interconnectedness of all life forms (Butic and Ngidlo 1997; World Agroforestry 2020). This practice involves rituals that honor the environment and ensure its sustainable use (Camacho et al. 2016). Such practices demonstrate the efficacy of integrating cultural values with environmental management strategies, offering a model for contemporary conservation efforts (Butic and Ngidlo 1997; World Agroforestry 2020; Camacho et al. 2016).

Moreover, incorporating Indigenous perspectives into environmental management fosters greater respect and collabora-

tion between Indigenous communities and policymakers (Butic and Ngidlo 1997; World Agroforestry 2020; Camacho et al. 2016). This integration can lead to more inclusive and culturally sensitive environmental policies crucial for achieving sustainable development goals. The revitalization of Indigenous practices, supported by research and policy initiatives, can contribute significantly to global efforts to combat climate change and promote ecological resilience (Hernandez et al., 2022).

Indigenous Knowledge Systems

Indigenous cultures worldwide have developed complex systems of environmental stewardship deeply rooted in their spiritual and cultural beliefs (Beckford et al. 2010; Fiveable 2024). These systems are not merely practices but are embedded in a worldview that perceives nature as sacred and interconnected with human life. In the Philippines, indigenous knowledge has been acknowledged for its role in sustaining production systems, with numerous studies validating its technical and scientific reliability. It was not until the 1992 Earth Summit that the Philippine government formally recognized the potential of these indigenous knowledge systems. Before this, researchers, development workers, and lawmakers in the Philippines focused on finding "modern" methods to achieve their goals.

Research shows that Indigenous practices, such as traditional fire management and rotational farming, effectively preserve biodiversity and prevent environmental degradation (Smith et al. 2024). These methods, informed by centuries of observation and experience, often outperform modern techniques in terms of sustainability and resilience. For instance, cultural burning, practiced by various Indigenous groups, helps reduce fuel loads, prevent large-scale wildfires, and enhance biodiversity (Adlam et al. 2022). Such practices highlight Indigenous traditions' deep environmental knowledge and efficacy in contemporary conservation efforts.

Traditional Environmental Practices

The Ifugao's *muyong* system is a traditional forest management practice where privately owned woodlots are carefully

tended to provide essential resources like water, fuel, and food. The term "*muyung*" describes privately owned woodlots among the Tawali subgroup of the Ifugao. This system reflects Ifugao's deep cultural connection to the environment, combining sustainable silviculture, agroforestry, and natural regeneration techniques to maintain the health of the forest and surrounding agricultural terraces. The *muyong* supports their physical needs and preserves their cultural practices and ecological balance (Camacho et al. 2012).

Furthermore, the *lapat* system is a traditional forest conservation strategy practiced by the Isneg and Tingguian peoples of Abra Province in the Philippines (Molintas 2004). It involves designating specific forest areas as off-limits to resource extraction for a period ranging from a few months to several years, depending on the area's need for ecological recovery. This practice helps in the natural regeneration of forests by allowing trees, plants, and wildlife to recover from previous disturbances.

During the *lapat* period, activities such as hunting, fishing, and gathering are prohibited, with some systems also imposing restrictions on harvesting specific plant and animal species (Molintas 2002). The *lapat* system is an effective way to sustainably manage natural resources and ensure their availability for future generations, as seen in areas like Bucloc, where it is enforced through both customary and local laws with designated individuals responsible for monitoring compliance (Camacho et al. 2012).

Dolom and Serrano (2005) also mentioned that the *Ikalahans*, a subgroup of the Ifugao tribe in the Caraballo Mountains, have developed a range of traditional practices for sustainable agriculture and water conservation. According to Walpole et al. (1993), their agricultural methods include the *Inum-an* system, which involves site selection, clearing, burning, planting, weeding, harvesting, and following to maintain soil fertility and productivity. *Gengen* or terracing combined with composting and *Day-og*, a composting technique, are used to conserve soil and nutrients. The *Balkah* system employs vegetative terracing with tiger grass to prevent soil erosion. *Kinebbah* involves leaving fields fallow to restore fertility (Dolinen 1995; Camacho et al.

2012). *Tuping* refers to rock walls built to prevent soil erosion. *Pamettey*, a homemade pesticide made from local plants and ash, is used to protect crops from pests. These traditional methods reflect the *Ikalahans'* deep understanding of their environment and commitment to sustainable land management. (Dolom and Serrano 2005; Camacho et al. 2012).

Dictaan-Bang-oa (2010) highlights the sustainable water management practices of the Kankanaey in Besao, Northern Philippines, which are deeply rooted in traditional religious beliefs and customary laws. Central to these practices are principles such as *inayan*, a moral code discouraging harmful actions, and reverence for *nakinbaey*, spiritual beings associated with water sources, which ensure the sustainable use of natural resources. Rituals like *legleg* and communal systems such as *dumapat* facilitate equitable water distribution and resource maintenance through collective decision-making and labor-sharing. Complementary to these cultural practices, the community uses sustainable forestry, including reforestation and selective logging, to protect water sources. Despite challenges from resource disputes and modern agricultural demands, these Indigenous frameworks—blending cultural traditions with local governance—demonstrate the resilience and adaptability of the Kankanaey in preserving ecological balance and communal well-being (Dictaan-Bang-oa 2010).

The Kankanaeys practice a mindful approach to keeping their water clean. They refrain from spitting and using soap or chemicals near their water sources. Even the remains of humans or animals are not permitted to pass through these areas. Offending the *nakinbaey* can lead to the abandonment of the water source, resulting in a reduced supply or a complete cutoff (Dictaan-Bang- oa 2010). Therefore, it is crucial to hold a cleansing ritual led by community elders, with all water users participating, to honor and appease the *nakinbaey* that resides in the water source.

The significance of water in Kankanaey life is also expressed in local poetry, such as the piece presented by Gaongen (2022) at the George Town Literary Festival in Malaysia, titled *The Strength of Water*. This poem highlights water's dual nature:

its capacity to cause destruction, like a tsunami, and its ability to restore and sustain life in the village, emphasizing its importance even in the "elders' prayers." Abance (2020) features thirty-three rituals from the Benguet Kankanaey that incorporate water as a vital element. Other rituals not included in her book but discussed in interviews and recordings also highlight water use, such as *basabas*, *dasadas*, *sepyat*, and more. Doctolero (2021) notes that mainstream society often dismisses the Kankanaeys' rituals and belief systems, which label them paganism. Many educated individuals and families from the Cordillera peoples express that they have neglected and abandoned their cultural beliefs, leading to a sense of alienation from their heritage. Some educational and church institutions even reject cultural identity. A less informed perspective claims that these cultural beliefs and traditions are manifestations of evil. Consequently, many indigenous people feel confused and uncomfortable showcasing their practices and beliefs.

However, traditional forest management practices face various challenges and threats (Camacho et al., 2012). *Muyong* owners enhance depleted areas through enrichment planting but often rely on fast-growing exotic species due to the scarcity of native seedlings, risking biodiversity loss. Development projects have also led to inappropriate practices, such as clearing *muyong* forests for non-traditional uses. The Ifugao Rice Terraces, crucial for water management, are deteriorating due to inadequate site management and declining local interest. The *lapat* system in Abra faces threats from pilferage. Meanwhile, the *Ikalahans* have effectively used their traditional practices, such as terracing and composting, to manage and conserve forests despite past threats from land conversion (Camacho et al. 2012).

Rituals and Ceremonies: Integrating Spiritual Beliefs with Sustainable Practices

The Indigenous cosmology of the Cordillera in the Philippines is rooted in a profound understanding of the interconnectedness between humans, nature, and the spiritual realm (Del Castillo et al., 2022). This worldview is reflected in the Cordilleran peoples' daily practices and environmental stewardship, who view the natural world as a living entity imbued with spiritual

significance.

For instance, Jacoba and Dubao (2022) presented the central role of the *emambunong* in the traditional culture of Benguet, particularly in Kabayan. The *emambunong* is deeply respected within the community as a mediator between the human and spiritual realms. Their role is integral to maintaining harmony and addressing transgressions involving spirits, especially during sacrificial rites. Spirits are seen as coexisting with the human community, particularly in sacred places such as Mount Pulag. This belief underscores the interconnectedness of the physical and spiritual worlds in indigenous traditions, with the *emambunong* facilitating communication and ensuring the community's adherence to cultural and spiritual norms (Clemente 2002; Jacoba and Dubao 2022). For example, The Kankana-ey, Ifugao, Bontoc, and Tingguian peoples of the Cordillera share a deep spiritual connection to their land, with each group practicing sustainable traditions tied to the environment (Igorotage, n.d.; Aswang Project-2 2024). The Kankana-ey honor the spirits of mountains, rivers, and forests through rituals and agriculture. The Ifugao view their sacred rice terraces as a symbol of harmony with nature celebrated through rituals like the *Hudhud* epic (Igorotage, n.d.; Aswang Project-2 2024). The Bontoc and Tingguian also revere ancestral spirits in natural spaces, using ceremonies like the *Pechen* peace pact and *Gawīga* when myths to maintain harmony between the human and spiritual worlds (Igorotage, n.d.; Aswang Project-2 2024).

In Cordilleran cosmology, the natural world is deeply intertwined with the spiritual realm. Indigenous beliefs hold that humans, nature, and spirits are interconnected in a delicate balance. This interconnectedness is central to their environmental practices, where maintaining harmony with nature and its spirits is crucial. Indigenous groups believe that disrupting this balance can lead to ecological and spiritual consequences (Jacoba and Dubao 2022; Aswang Project 2018).

Essential spiritual beliefs guide these practices. For instance, ancestral spirits, known as *anito*, are revered as guardians of the land and its resources (Jacoba and Dubao, 2022). These spirits are believed to influence the community's well-

being, and maintaining a harmonious relationship with them is essential for prosperity (Igorotage, 2024; Jacoba and Dubao, 2022). Nature deities, associated with rivers, mountains, and forests, also play a significant role. Rituals and offerings honor these deities, ensuring their favor is retained and natural resources are used sustainably (Chunhabunyatip et al. 2018). For example, the dance rituals performed to honor spirits are integral to agricultural practices. During these ceremonies, offerings are made to appease the spirits and seek their blessings for a bountiful harvest. Such rituals reflect the deep spiritual connection between the Cordillerans and their environment, underscoring the role of spirituality in guiding environmental stewardship (Fiar-od 2021).

Syncretism in Beliefs and Practices

Syncretism in the Cordillera region showcases the merging of Indigenous beliefs with Christian teachings, resulting in a distinctive blend of spiritual practices. A prominent example of this syncretism is the combination of Christian rituals with indigenous ceremonies. For instance, the traditional Ifugao ritual that honors ancestral spirits, which includes offerings and prayers for a fruitful harvest, has been adapted to incorporate Christian prayers and hymns while preserving the essential spiritual intent of the ceremony (Igorotage 2024). Likewise, the influence of the Catholic church is evident in how indigenous communities observe Christian holidays like Christmas and Easter, often integrating indigenous symbols and practices, such as traditional dances or rituals, alongside Christian elements (Agbayani 1993).

Cordillera rituals, deeply rooted in indigenous knowledge and oral tradition, remain integral to the Igorots' daily lives, blending customary laws, ancestral practices, and Christian influences introduced during colonization. Rituals serve diverse purposes, from seeking blessings and expressing gratitude to appeasing spirits and fostering community solidarity. They often involve prayers, chants, animal sacrifices, and symbolic props like rice, fire, and carved figures to convey spiritual and environmental harmony. Elders or designated officiants, respected for their cultural knowledge and integrity, lead these ceremonies, reflecting moral values and practical customs, such as land

rights acquisition and conflict resolution. Despite modernization and migration affecting these practices, rituals significantly preserve cultural identity, environmental stewardship, and spiritual connection among Cordillera communities (Fiar-od 2021).

Implications and Challenges of Indigenous Environmental Stewardship

The increasing acknowledgment of Indigenous environmental practices underscores their significance for global ecological management, particularly in an accelerating climate crisis. Bennett et al. (2018) suggest that incorporating Indigenous knowledge into contemporary environmental strategies bolsters conservation and sustainable development efforts. Furthermore, Black and McBean (2016) emphasize that enhancing Indigenous involvement in environmental decision-making can improve health outcomes and conservation initiatives. By integrating Indigenous viewpoints, policies can become more inclusive and culturally attuned, promoting effective and equitable environmental management that leverages the deep ecological insights of these communities.

However, the Cordillera region faces significant challenges due to industrial activities like mining and deforestation, which threaten traditional practices and local ecosystems. Mining has led to land degradation, disrupted traditional agricultural and forest management systems, and caused soil erosion and water contamination, undermining Indigenous practices' sustainability (Camacho 2012; Timblique 2024;).

Additionally, external pressures from government policies and commercial interests often worsen these problems, placing economic development above environmental conservation and neglecting Indigenous land rights, further marginalizing these communities (Amnesty International 2024). In response, it is crucial to implement efforts to preserve Indigenous knowledge, such as educational programs and community-based initiatives, to revitalize traditional practices and incorporate them into modern environmental management (Laltoog 2024 2018; Mekonnen et al. 2022; Fiar-od 2021; Pappalardo 2020).

Reclaiming Cultural Identity

I would like to argue that securing land rights and enacting laws to regulate environmental degradation is no longer enough for ecological well-being. Restoring the spiritual and emotional ties between people and their land is crucial for the community to thrive. This task is both a religious and cultural challenge. The task must re-emphasize that Indigenous peoples worldwide should profoundly re-connect to their environment, viewing it as the foundation of their lives, spirituality, and cultural identity (Carling 2001). Indigenous worldview must, once again, re-emphasize collective coexistence, mutual respect, and cooperation, contrasting Western resource-centric approaches (Carling 2001).

Reclaiming the lost identity can also mean integrating Indigenous environmental practices with modern conservation. In this way, efforts to promote environmental preservation offer a promising approach to sustainable development in Cordillera. Developed over generations, Indigenous knowledge provides valuable insights into local ecosystems and sustainable resource management. For example, Ifugao's *muyong* system for managing forests surrounding rice terraces is an effective conservation practice that can complement contemporary approaches to forest and agricultural sustainability (Molintas 2004).

Moreover, collaboration between Indigenous communities, government agencies, and NGOs is crucial in blending traditional wisdom with scientific research, creating more effective conservation strategies (Pappalardo 2020). Reaffirming cultural identity through environmental stewardship is crucial for strengthening community resilience. Practices intertwined with cultural rituals, such as agricultural and forest management ceremonies, maintain a strong sense of identity and social cohesion (Laltoog 2024). Balancing tradition with modern challenges, such as climate change, further enhances the relevance of these practices in contemporary conservation (Mekonnen et al., 2022).

CONCLUSION

The indigenous beliefs and practices in the Cordillera play

a crucial role in environmental stewardship, showcasing a profound connection between people, nature, and the spiritual world. Traditional methods such as the *muyong* forest management system and sacred rituals associated with land and water emphasize sustainability and reverence for natural resources. However, the rise of modernization, industrialization, outside pressures, and greedy profit-oriented individuals threaten these practices.

It is now the time to realize that a significant opportunity exists to merge indigenous knowledge with contemporary conservation efforts, leading to more effective environmental strategies that honor cultural heritage. Collaboration among indigenous communities, policymakers, and NGOs is essential for this integration, ensuring that conservation policies are inclusive and impactful. It is not just a matter of an appeal, but rather, a categorical imperative that as we move forward, policymakers guarantee that the beliefs and the rights of Indigenous communities are upheld amid development. Similarly, Indigenous communities are to adopt a more critical stance on receiving the Christian faith, adopting its life-giving elements, and vehemently resisting all death-dealing elements. It is also essential to engage private and public academic institutions to create a curriculum to aid in preserving cultural heritage while addressing the challenges of the climate crisis. These are vital concerns for political, religious, and academic stakeholders. Additionally, it is an urgent call to all the Cordilleras to say enough to the oppressive systems and practices that slowly and gradually kill the life-giving elements of Indigenous beliefs and practices. In reclaiming the lost identity, one must resist all death-giving elements introduced by modernity and the selfish capitalist mentality. Nobody owns nature; we are nature. To destroy nature is to destroy ourselves.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. **Integrating Indigenous Knowledge with Contemporary Conservation Efforts:** There is an urgent need to blend indigenous ecological practices with modern conservation strategies. This integration will ensure that environmen-

tal policies are both effective and culturally respectful, leveraging the deep environmental wisdom inherent in Indigenous practices like the *muyong* forest management system.

2. **Collaborative Frameworks:** Policymakers, Indigenous communities, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) must establish collaborative frameworks that respect and uphold Indigenous rights. This cooperation should focus on creating inclusive conservation strategies that reflect the values and practices of Indigenous peoples.
3. **Policy Advocacy:** Policymakers need to guarantee the protection of Indigenous rights in the face of development pressures. Legislation must prioritize the preservation of Indigenous beliefs and practices as integral to sustainable environmental management (Adlam 2021).
4. **Critical Reception of External Influences:** Indigenous communities should critically engage with external influences, particularly the adoption of Christianity. Embracing its positive elements while resisting those that undermine Indigenous values will foster a balanced and respectful cultural syncretism.
5. **Educational Curriculum Development:** Academic institutions should develop curricula that incorporate Indigenous knowledge systems, aiming to preserve cultural heritage and address contemporary environmental challenges. This approach will educate future generations on the importance of cultural and environmental stewardship.
6. **Community Mobilization:** Indigenous communities need to mobilize against oppressive systems and practices that threaten their traditional ways of life. Collective action is necessary to resist the detrimental impacts of modernization and capitalist exploitation on their cultural and environmental legacy.
7. **Environmental Awareness Campaigns:** Initiatives to raise awareness about the interconnectedness of humans and nature should be prioritized. These campaigns can help shift mindsets towards a more sustainable and respectful relationship with the environment.

8. Inclusive Development Models: Development models should be inclusive, ensuring that Indigenous voices are heard and respected. This inclusivity will promote development that is both sustainable and equitable, preserving the life-giving elements of Indigenous beliefs and practices.

These recommendations aim to foster a harmonious relationship between Indigenous cultural practices and modern environmental stewardship, ensuring the sustainability of both cultural heritage and natural resources. By respecting and integrating Indigenous knowledge, we can create a more sustainable future that honors and preserves the rich cultural legacy of the Cordillera.

REFERENCES

- Adivasi.org. (2024, October). *Embracing tribal wisdom: Living in harmony with nature*. <https://www.adivasi.org/blogs/embracing-tribal-wisdom-living-in-harmony-with-nature>
- Abad, R. G. (2004). *The Asian face of globalization: Reconstructing identities, institutions, and resources: The work of the 2001/2002 API fellows*. Tokyo: Nippon Foundation.
- Abance, S. (2020). *Ated: Understanding timeless values ingrained within a fading Kankanaey tradition*. Baguio City: Messenger of Hope.
- Abordo, C., & Coronacion, D. (2019). The construction of Indigenous lands and domains in the Cordillera and its impact on the quest for regional autonomy. *ASSEMBLEA: An Online Journal of Political Science*, 1(1), 1-19.
- Acabado, S. (2017). The archaeology of pericolonialism: Responses of the "unconquered" to Spanish conquest and colonialism in Ifugao, Philippines. *International Journal of Historical Archaeology*, 21(1), 1-26.
- Adlam, C., Almendariz, D., Goode, R. W., Martinez, D. J., & Middleton, B. R. (2021). Keepers of the Flame: Supporting the Revitalization of Indigenous Cultural Burning. *Society & Natural Resources*, 35(5), 575-590. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2021.2006385>

Agbayani, R. (1993). Some Indigenous cultural traditions in the

- Philippines: Their implications for environmental conservation. *Kasarinlan: Journal of New Thinking on Philippine Social Issues*, 9(1), 54-69.
- Aguilar, J. F. (2018). The role of culture in Indigenous peoples' education: A case study of Cordillera schools. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 6, 8-15. Google Scholar.
- Allad-iw, A. L. (2014, October 28). Ancestral land rights to own, use & control resources: A must for Cordillera autonomy. *Cordillera Peoples Alliance*. <https://cpaphils.wordpress.com/>
- Amnesty International. (2024, November 30). Indigenous peoples. *Amnesty International*. <https://www.amnesty.org/en/what-we-do/indigenous-peoples/>
- Anacin, C. J. G. (2009). A descriptive and socio-cultural analysis of Ibaloi death ritual, music, and performance with emphasis on the symbolic context and representation. PhD diss., University of the Philippines Baguio.
- Aswang Project. (2018, October 25). Cordilleran beliefs. *The Aswang Project*. Accessed November 18, 2024, from <https://www.aswangproject.com/philippine-mythology/cordilleran-beliefs/>
- Aswang Project. (2024). Kankanaey beliefs. *The Aswang Project*. Retrieved from https://www.aswangproject.com/philippine-mythology/cordilleran-beliefs/kankanaey-beliefs/#google_vignette
- Auger, M. D. (2016). Cultural continuity as a determinant of Indigenous peoples' health. *International Indigenous Policy Journal*, 7(4), 1-24.
- Beckford, C. L., Jacobs, C., Williams, N., & Nahdee, R. (2010). Aboriginal environmental wisdom, stewardship, and sustainability: Lessons from the Walpole Island First Nations, Ontario, Canada. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 41(4), 239-248.
- Bennett, N. J., Whitty, T. S., Finkbeiner, E., Pittman, J., Bassett, H., Gelcich, S., & Allison, E. H. (2018). Environmental stewardship: A conceptual review and analytical framework. *Envi-*

ronmental Management, 61(5), 597-614. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-017-0993-2>

Black, K., & McBean, E. (2016). Increased Indigenous participation in environmental decision-making: A policy analysis for the improvement of Indigenous health. *International Indigenous Policy Journal*, 7(4). <https://doi.org/10.18584/iipj.2016.7.4.5>

Britannica. (2024). Igorot. *Encyclopaedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Igorot>

Buchler, I. R., & Rossi, I. (1980). *People in culture: A survey of cultural anthropology*. New York: Praeger.

Butic, M., & Ngidlo, R. (1997). *Muyong forest of Ifugao: Assisted natural regeneration in traditional forest management*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Retrieved from <https://www.fao.org/4/AD466E/ad466e06.htm>

Camacho, L. D., Combalicer, M. S., Yeo-Chang, Y., Combalicer, E. A., Carandang, A. P., Camacho, S. C., ... & Rebugio, L. L. (2012). Traditional forest conservation knowledge/technologies in the Cordillera, Northern Philippines. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 22, 3-8.

Carling, J. (2001, October). The Cordillera experience. *Asia Society*. <https://asiasociety.org/cordillera-experience>

Celino, S. (1990). Death and burial rituals and other practices and beliefs of the Cordillerans (Ph.D. diss., University of Baguio, Benguet, Philippines). *Google Scholar*.

Champagne, D. (2007). *Social change and cultural continuity among native nations*. Lanham, NY; Toronto; Plymouth, UK: Altamira Press.

Chunhabunyatip, P., Sasaki, N., Grünbühel, C., Kuwornu, J. K. M., & Tsusaka, T. W. (2018). Influence of Indigenous spiritual beliefs on natural resource management and ecological conservation in Thailand. *Sustainability*, 10(8), 2842. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10082842>

Clemente, N. (2002, February 18). Playground of the gods. *Philippine Center for Investigative Journalism*. Retrieved No-

vember 18, 2024, from <https://old.pcij.org/stories/playground-of-the-gods/>

Cordillera Peoples Alliance. (2023, November 30). Cordillera Peoples Alliance. *Asia Land Coalition*. <https://asia.landcoalition.org/en/our-network/cordillera-peoples-alliance/>

Course Hero. (2024). *The Cordillera people right to land*. <https://www.coursehero.com/file/201009810/SSPT-LAND-RIGHTS-OF-THE-CORDILLERA-PEOPLEpdf/>

de Satgé, R. (2023). Indigenous and community land rights. In D. Mamo (Ed.), *International Working Group for Indigenous Affairs (IWGIA)*. <https://landportal.org/issues/indigenous-community-land-rights2>

Del Castillo, F. A., Edara, I. R., Ching, G. S., Molino, J., Jacoba, R., & Del Castillo, C. D. B. (2023). Religiosity among Indigenous peoples: A study of Cordilleran youth in the Philippines. *Religions*, 14(6), 751. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel14060751>

Dictaan-Bang-oa, E. (2010). Traditional water management practices of the Kankanaey: *Cultural Survival Quarterly*. <https://www.culturalsurvival.org/publications/cultural-survival-quarterly/traditional-water-management-practices-kankanaey>

Dimonye, S. C. (2024). The contributions of modern capitalism to modernity: Focus on the philosophical perspectives on development. *Authorea Preprints*.

Fiveable. (2024). Indigenous stewardship. *Fiveable Library*. <https://library.fiveable.me/indigenous-issues-across-the-americas/unit-7/indigenous-environmental-stewardship-conservation/study-guide/G1MoUEuZDVthGNuc>

Fiveable. (2024). *Sacredness of Nature*. <https://library.fiveable.me/native-people-their-environment/unit-4/sacred-sites-ecological-significance/study-guide/K3Ky1ObHPgHMPwoC>

Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). (2013). Indigenous peoples' food systems and well-being. Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/3/i3144e/i3144e00.htm>

- Friedl, J., & Pfeiffer, J. E. (1977). *Anthropology*. New York: Harper's College Press.
- Gaongen, G. (2022, November). The strength of water. *Words Without Borders*. <https://wordswithoutborders.org/read/article/2022-11/the-strength-of-water-gawani-gaongen/>
- Global Diversity Foundation. (2021, November 30). Reviving culture and ritual for conservation of land, local ecosystems, and sacred natural sites. *Global Diversity Foundation*. <https://global-diversity.org/2021/11/30/reviving-culture-and-ritual-for-conservation-of-land-local-ecosystems-and-sacred-natural-sites/>
- Halim, C., Wan Nurul Mardiah Wan Mohd Rani, & Nurul Asma' Mokhtar. (2017). Examining community engagement in heritage conservation through Geopark experiences from the Asia Pacific region. *Kajian Malaysia*, 35(Supp. 1), 11–38. <https://doi.org/10.21315/km2017.35.suppl.1.2>
- Hernandez, J., Meisner, J., Bardosh, K., & Rabinowitz, P. (2022). Prevent pandemics and halt climate change? Strengthen land rights for indigenous peoples. *Lancet Planetary Health*, 6(5), e381–e382. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(22\)00236-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(22)00236-0)
- ICBE. (n.d.). Cordillera rituals: Their features and significance. *ICBE - Cordillera Rituals as a Way of Life*. Retrieved from <https://www.icbe.eu/cordillera-rituals-as-a-way-of-life/948-cordillera-rituals-their-features-and-significance>
- Igorotage. (2024). The Igorot ethnic groups. *Igorotage* <https://www.igorotage.com>
- Igorotage. (2024, January 27). The Kankana-ey people of the Cordilleras. *Igorotage*. <https://www.igorotage.com/blog/kankana-ey-people>
- IWGIA. (2024). Indigenous peoples' human rights defenders forge solidarity amid rising challenges. Retrieved from <https://www.iwgia.org>
- Jacoba, R. C., & Dubao, B. (2022). A post-COVID-19 pandemic eco-spiritual grounding. *Journal of the Religion and Social Communication*, 20(2), 181.

- Kimmerer, R. W. (2013). *Braiding sweetgrass: Indigenous wisdom, scientific knowledge, and the teachings of plants*. Minneapolis: Milkweed Editions.
- Laltoog, B. (2024). Empowering indigenous communities: The pursuit of quality education and peaceful societies. *Inclusive Society and Sustainability Studies*, 4(1), 43–56. <https://doi.org/10.31098/issues.v4i1.2055>
- Laugrand, F., Laugrand, A., Tamang, J., & Magapin, G. (2020). Exchanges with the dead: Exhuming human remains among the Ibaloy of Upper Loacan (Philippines). *Bijdragen tot de taal-, land- en volkenkunde/Journal of the Humanities and Social Sciences of Southeast Asia*, 176(4), 475–503.
- Wikipedia. (2024, November 18). *Ibaloi people*. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ibaloi>
- Lynch, O. J. (2011). Indigenous peoples' land rights in the Philippines. *Cultural Survival Quarterly Magazine*, 35(4). Retrieved from <https://www.culturalsurvival.org/publications/cultural-survival-quarterly/ancestral-land-and-cultural-survival>
- Mekonnen, H., Bires, Z., & Berhanu, K. (2022). Practices and challenges of cultural heritage conservation in historical and religious heritage sites: Evidence from North Shoa Zone, Amhara Region, Ethiopia. *Heritage Science*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-022-00802-6>
- Molino, J. N. (2022). An exploration of Cordilleran students' Christian environmentalism (CE) and environmental awareness (EA): Towards a post-COVID-19 pandemic response to Laudato Si'. *Journal of the Asian Research Center for Religion and Social Communication*, 20, 224. [Google Scholar]
- Molintas, B. (2019). *Inayan, a cultural indigeneity: Coping strategies for Igorot indigenous people and ethics in individualist organizations*. La Jolla: Northcentral University.
- NativeTribe.info. (n.d.). Igorot tribe: Philippines culture, history, and traditions
- Pacos, C. A. (2018, April 20). Cordillera Peoples Alliance: Land is life, the struggle continues. *Agshan Online*. <https://>

agshanonline2018.wordpress.com/2018/04/20/cordillera-peoples-alliance-land-is-life-the-struggle-continues/

Pappalardo, G. (2020). Community-based processes for revitalizing heritage: Questioning justice in the experimental practice of ecomuseums. *Sustainability*, 12(21), 9270. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12219270>

Patterson, H., Bowles, E., Chiblow, S., McGregor, D., Kozmik, C., & Popp, J. N. (2023). Environmental and socio-cultural impacts of glyphosate-based herbicides: Perspectives from Indigenous knowledge and Western science. *Frontiers in Conservation Science*, 4, 1186399. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcosc.2023.1186399>

Peterson, W. (2010). Performing indigeneity in the Cordillera: Dance, community, and power in the highlands of Luzon. *Asian Theatre Journal*, 27(2), 246–268. <http://www.jstor.com/stable/25782119>

Pollock, L. (2020). How capitalism is a driving force of climate change. *The People, Ideas, and Things Journal, Special Issue: Pandemics & Politics*. <https://pitjournal.unc.edu/2022/12/24/how-capitalism-is-a-driving-force-of-climate-change/>

PSA-CAR. (2024, June 27). Land ownership in the Cordillera Administrative Region (2020 Census of Population and Housing). *Release Number SSR 2024-19*. <https://rssocar.psa.gov.ph/content/land-ownership-cordillera-administrative-region-2020-census-population-and-housing>

Rimando, M. A. (2015, May 28). Potentials and challenges in the Cordillera Administrative Region. Paper presented at the *Regional Conference on Industry Roadmaps and AEC Game Plan: Roadmap Localization for Competitiveness*, Baguio Country Club, Baguio City. Retrieved from <https://mabikas-foundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/CAR-Potentials-and-Challenges-Rimando.pdf>

Ryser, R. C. (2011). Indigenous peoples and traditional knowledge. *Center for World Indigenous Studies*. Retrieved from <https://www.cwis.org/document/indigenous-peoples->

and- traditional-knowledge/

Saint Louis University. (n.d.). History & institutional statements. <https://www.slu.edu.ph/history/>

Santiago, L. (2013). The right to land: The struggles of the Cordillera Peoples in the Philippines. *United Nations Human Rights Office of the High Commissioner*. Retrieved from https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/Documents/Issues/IPeoples/EMRIP/RightToLand_SantiagoPhilippinesCordillera.pdf

Scott, W. H. (1988). *A Sagada reader*. New Day Publishers.

Scott, W. H. (1974). *The discovery of the Igorots: Spanish contacts with the pagans of Northern Luzon*. Quezon City: New Day Publishers.

Scott, W. H. (1977). *The discovery of the Igorots: Spanish contacts with the pagans of Northern Luzon*. Quezon City: New Day Publishers.

Sinthumule, N. I. (2023). Traditional ecological knowledge and its role in biodiversity conservation: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 11, 1164900. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2023.1164900>

Sitabayasi, H. (2022). Beliefs of Kankana-ey and a contextualization of the Gospel. *Asian Journal of Pentecostal Studies*, 25 (2).

Smith, C., Ainscough, J., Alare, R. S., Croker, A. R., De Freitas, K. M., Millington, J. D., & Yadav, K. (2024). How policy interventions influence burning to meet cultural and small-scale livelihood objectives. *Ecology and Society*, 29(1). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-13492-2901>

Sterling, G. E. (2024, December 8). From the dean's desk. *Reflections: Crucified Creation: A Green Faith Rising*. <https://reflections.yale.edu/article/crucified-creation-green-faith-rising/dean-s-desk>

Sumeg-ang, A. (2005). The Ibaloys. In *Ethnography of the major ethnolinguistic groups in the Cordillera* (pp. 28–51). New Day Publishers.

- Taray, L. L. (2008). Understanding ancestor reverence in the Benguet tradition. *Asia-Pacific Social Science Review*, 8(1), 61–72.
- Tauli-Corpuz, V. (2015). *Country technical notes on Indigenous Peoples' issues: Philippines*. International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD).
- Timblique, J. (2024). Case study: The environmental and social costs of illegal mining in the Cordillera region of the Philippines. *SSRN Working Paper*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4964066>
- Ting, M. T. G. J., Bagsic, A. C., Equilos-Ryan Jaen, M. M., Respi-cio, M. L. P., & Tan, C. R. T. (2008). Modernity vs. culture: Protecting the Indigenous Peoples of the Philippines. *European Journal of Economic and Political Studies*, 1(1), 77–98.
- United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Di-
vision for Social Policy and Development, Secretariat of the
Permanent Forum on Indigenous Issues. (2009). *State of the
world's Indigenous Peoples* (ST/ESA/328). United Nations.
[https://www.un.org/esa/socdev/unpfii/documents/SOWIP/
en/SOWIP_web.pdf](https://www.un.org/esa/socdev/unpfii/documents/SOWIP/en/SOWIP_web.pdf)
- Walpole, P., Braganza, G., Ong, J. B., Tengco, G. J., & Wijanco,
E. (Eds.). (1993). *Upland Philippine communities: Guardians
of the final forest frontiers* (Research Network Report No. 4).
Center for Southeast Asia Studies, University of California,
Berkeley.
- Wieber, M. (1993). *Politics, property, and law in the Philippine
uplands*. Wilfrid Laurier University Press.
- World Agroforestry. (2020, May 30). Science and tradition: How
Indigenous communities manage forests. [https://
worldagroforestry.org/blog/2020/05/30/science-and-
tradition-how-indigenous-communities-manage-forests](https://worldagroforestry.org/blog/2020/05/30/science-and-tradition-how-indigenous-communities-manage-forests)
- World Bank. (2021). *Indigenous Peoples in the Philippines*.
[https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/philippines/brief/
indigenous-peoples](https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/philippines/brief/indigenous-peoples)
- Yahaya, A. (2012). Indigenous knowledge in the management of
a community-based forest reserve in the West District of Gha-

